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JOB SATISFACTION OF TEACHER EDUCATORS OF PRIVATE EDUCATION COLLEGES OF DELHI NCR IN RELATION TO CERTAIN VARIABLES

*Sanjeev Kumar Jha **Prof. Sohrab Ali

ABSTRACT

The research was an attempt to study the job satisfaction of private teacher's educators. The sample comprised of 90 teacher educators of Delhi NCR with the use of simple random sampling technique. The sample was administered by a standardized "Teacher Job Satisfaction" tool by Yudhvirendera Mudgil, Prof. I.S. Muhar & Prabha Bhatia in 1991 was employed. The collected data statistically analysed for this measure of central tendencies and 't' were used. Result of the research revealed that i) The overall teacher educators of Delhi NCR have moderate level of job satisfaction. ii) The female teacher's educators have higher job satisfaction than their male counter parts. iii) Experience and Salary positively affect the job satisfaction.

Introduction

Teacher is a dynamic person, who plays a vital role in the development of an individual into a better teacher. The challenge to the teacher is that of helping a learner retain his identity, develop his individuality and absorb background of democratic culture (Crow and Crow, 1992). Keeping in view the importance of the teaching profession, it is always desirable to select such a person for this job who is equipped with the needed attributes of an ideal and competent teacher. Along with it there should be necessary facilities for him so that he must enjoy his profession.

The concept

Privatization of teacher education has undoubtedly provided enormous opportunity to the graduates to get training of one of the noblest profession. But it increased a hidden competition among management of teacher education colleges. Ironically that is who will pay less salary and run their colleges more profitably. The teaching in these colleges with high job satisfaction is really a hard nut to crack. The quality of teacher education colleges largely depends upon the job satisfaction of their teachers. Job life is one of the important parts of an individual's life any problem at job place causes stress in life. It may adversely affect the productivity. For proper productivity the job satisfaction is prerequisite.

Job satisfaction may be defined as the extent to which an employee like (satisfaction) or dislike (dissatisfaction) his jobs. A pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job can be a determinant of job satisfaction. Job satisfaction includes some general things like perception towards profession, job security, pay, coworker, supervisions and personal growth. J.A. Rajaregam and Dr. I. Christie Doss (2011) found that present level of job satisfaction of teachers of engineering colleges in Pondicherry is high. Bhuyan, B and Choudhury, M. (2002) found that 1) there is no association of levels of job satisfaction with gender, marital status, experience of the college teachers, and locality of the institution. 2) They were not happy with the facilities (like classrooms, library, laboratory, teaching aids etc.) existing syllabus and curriculum. Teachers had a positive attitude towards professional development and strong belief that M.Phil., Ph.D. research work and in-service training like refresher courses, orientation programme, summer course etc. 3) teachers had strongly opinion that only meritorious people should be appointed in the teaching profession through NET or equivalent State Level Selection Board. Chandraiah, K (1994) found that 1) age and job satisfaction

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had significant positive relationship among younger, middle and old aged groups. 2) It was observed that correlation coefficients obtained for the subjects age and job satisfaction, tenure of service and age, job satisfaction and tenure of the service were all positive and significant.

Need of the study

Teacher Educator is one who trains an individual and develops him as a teacher which is itself a noble profession. So being a teacher educator is a responsible job. If teacher educators do not like and feel stress at their work place then one can understand the quality of their products. So job satisfaction is one of the instruments that determines/ enhances the quality of teacher education. In order to maintain the quality of these colleges job satisfaction of their teachers is prerequisite. There are number of factors at which job satisfaction depends. Strong belief that M.Phil., Ph.D. research work and in-service training like refresher courses, orientation programme, summer course etc. (Bhuyan, B and Choudhury, M., 2002). The privatization of teacher education has increased the demand of teacher educator so with this pace demand will be fulfilled that again depends upon the quality of teacher education colleges. It seems that some of the private teacher education colleges are not paying salaries and other benefit as per norms. In this changing scenario, the need of job satisfaction arises. It prompted the researcher to study the job satisfaction of teacher educator.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the job satisfaction of teacher Educators of Delhi NCR.
2. To study the job satisfaction of teacher educators of Delhi NCR in relation to the experiences.
3. To study the job satisfaction of teacher educators of Delhi NCR in relation to gender.
4. To study the Job Satisfaction of the teacher educators of Delhi NCR in relation to monthly salary.

Hypotheses of the study

- The teacher educators of Delhi NCR have high job satisfaction.
- There is no significant difference of job satisfaction in relation experiences of teacher educators of Delhi NCR.
- There is no significant difference of job satisfaction of teacher educator of Delhi NCR in relation to their gender.
- There is no significant difference of job satisfaction of teacher educator of Delhi NCR in relation to their monthly salary.

Methodology

Descriptive survey method was employed for the study All the Teacher Educators teaching in the Education colleges running in National Capital Region, the colleges in Delhi NCR having affiliation by Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University (GGIPU) Delhi, Chaudhary Charan Singh University (CCSU), Meerut (UP) and Maharshi Dayanand University (MDU), Rohtak (Haryana). 90 {5 teacher educators from each college X 6 Colleges (6 colleges from each university) X 3 University} Teacher educators were selected with the use of simple random sampling technique. Colleges were selected with purposive sampling technique. A standardized "Teacher Job Satisfaction" tool by Yudhvirendera Mudgil, Prof. I.S. Muhar & Prabha Bhatia in 1991 was employed.

Analysis and Interpretation

Hypothesis 1: The teacher educators of Delhi NCR have high job satisfaction.

Table 1.1 Job Satisfaction of Teacher Educator of Delhi NCR

S. No.	Number of Teacher Educator	Mean
1	90	223.54